

Modelling low-carbon energy pathways: Case of Senegal

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Executive Summary

As a signatory to the Paris Agreement, Senegal has been involved in the fight against climate change for some years now. With the aim of tackling climate risks while at the same time seizing opportunities for sobriety, sustainable policies have been developed by the central government in a number of sectors, including energy.

The energy sector is responsible for over 6165 Gg CO₂ of Senegal's emissions. Although measures are being taken to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, with over 30% of installed power coming from renewable sources, production is still dominated by fossil based thermal power plants, including heavy fuel oil, waste steam and diesel accounting for over 50%. In addition, Senegal plan to become a producer of oil and natural gas, with a large proportion dedicated to electricity generation under the government's Gas-To-Power strategy (2019). However, even if the government intends to strengthen its ambitions by increasing the penetration rate of renewable energies to 40% by 2030, with a joint target of 699MW (solar, wind and hydro) in additional electricity production (CDN, 2020), it is still certain that no electricity mix plan is available beyond this deadline (2030).

With a baseline scenario (BAU) and two additional scenarios (JETP and LoWC), this study aims to shed light on the implementation of the State's ambitions and the decarbonization of electricity production beyond 2030. In all, the decarbonization of electricity generation and the JETP each require an investment of more than 14 billion US dollars.

1. Introduction

Senegal is facing major energy challenges linked to the exploitation of hydrocarbon resources (oil and gas) and meeting its climate commitments. Since 2020, the country has submitted its Nationally Determined Contribution, with targets to reduce GHG emissions by 7% (NDC) and 29% (NDC+) by 2030. With strong mitigation measures in the energy sector (NDC, 2020).

Over the past few years, the country has been developing its electricity mix by increasing the penetration of renewable energies. Between 2018 and 2022, the share of renewable energies rose from 16% to over 30% (Ministry of Energy, 2023). Senegal recently signed the JETP (Just Energy Transition Partnership) agreement, with the aim of achieving a 40% electricity mix by 2030 in terms of installed capacity (Sarr et al., 2023).

The country's highly contrasting energy situation between achieving energy security and reducing GHG emissions raises questions about the outlook for the future. In view of the issues mentioned above, could the country explore scenarios such as JET-P with a 40% electricity mix ? and Can the country stop investing in the development of fossil-fired power stations from 2050 ?

2. Methodology

OSMOSYS is an open-source linear modeling system that can predict the optimal evolution of a country's energy matrix (Borges et al., 2024). In this work, the OSMOSYS tool is used in the sense that the model covers all energy sectors, including transport and heat. In addition, its ability to optimize power plant capacity expansions is a determining factor in this work.

In this exercise, we used energy production data provided by the annual balance sheet of the Ministry of Energy and electricity production data from the national electricity company over the period 2016 to 2021 (Energy balance, 2021; SENELEC, 2021)¹. Macroeconomic data for the same period are taken from the national statistics agency's resources and employment tables (ANSD, 2022)².

On this basis, our exercise focuses on three scenarios:

¹ : Each year the Ministry of Energy publishes an annual energy balance in Excel format

² : The National Statistics Agency publishes the value added by the country's overall GDP sector every year

- i) **BAU (Business As Usual)** : Baseline scenario, reflecting the country's current energy situation. This trend will be extended to 2050 without any additional measures. Energy supply and demand increase in a linear fashion. No assumptions are made about macroeconomic or demographic data.
- ii) **JETP (Just Energy Transition Partnership)** : this scenario reflects the Senegalese government's commitments under the recently signed JETP agreement. It targets a 40% penetration rate of renewable energies in electricity production by 2030. In addition to grid-connected generation, the model explores the potential of microgrids to meet energy demand in households and the agricultural sector.
- iii) **LoWC (Low Carbon)** : Like the previous scenario, this one promotes the development of renewable energies in electricity production. This last scenario in our work imposes a constraint that cancels all investment in the development of fossil electricity (HFP, coal, gas) beyond 2060. This does not mean that the country will end up with 100% renewable production; of course, existing fossil-fuel power stations will continue to operate, but no additional investment will be allocated to the development of fossil-fuel power stations.

3. Results

This long-term modelling work (2015-2065) has made it possible to assess four essential parameters for the development and implementation of a low-carbon strategy for the electricity sub-sector.

3.1. Power generation

Senegal's electricity production is expected to rise from less than 1PJ in 2015 to more than 12PJ in 2065, depending on the reference situation. An exponential increase in production to meet the growing demand from the productive sectors (industry, tertiary and transport) and households. With an average proportion of natural gas (CCGT), production is essentially dominated by renewable energies, particularly solar and onshore wind, which together account for more than half of production in the various scenarios. In the last two scenarios, the penetration of these energies begins in 2030, with rates of 40% for the JETP scenario and 57.7% for the LoWC scenario.

Figure 1 : Power generation (2015-2065)

3.2. Installed capacity

Between 2015 and 2065, Senegal's electricity generation capacity is essentially dominated by low-carbon energies, in particular renewable energies and natural gas. In all the scenarios, there is a rapid increase in the penetration rate of renewable energies from 2030 onwards. Solar photovoltaics (utility and distributed with storage) and onshore wind account for at least 40% in all the projections. At the same time, generation from petroleum products (LFO, HFO and diesel) and coal is virtually non-existent in all scenarios from 2030 onwards.

Figure 2 : Installed capacity

3.3. Emissions

The trend in greenhouse gas emissions remains similar in all the scenarios. There is a fast rise from 2015 onwards, then a peak followed by a sharp fall. For the BAU and JETP scenarios, the emission peaks are recorded in 2065 and 2066, corresponding to a renewable energy penetration of over 70%. This is a mitigation measure that contributes to the reduction of GHGs in the electricity sub-sector. In the LoWC scenario, emissions remain constant and then fall after investment in fossil electricity is halted.

Figure 3 : Annual emissions

3.4. Total Investment cost

In terms of the investment required to implement these trajectories, the LoWC is the most expensive, with a total cost of US\$14 731 million. It is slightly followed by the second scenario, which requires a total of US\$14 619 million. Without any additional constraints on current guidelines and policies, implementation of the BAU requires an investment of 1309 million US dollars.

However, the non-linearity in the evolution of emissions, where the last two scenarios were expected to generate less GHGs, is essentially due to the high use of coal and biomass. However, this requires a calibration of demand in other sectors, notably industry and the residential sector.

Figure 4 : Total Discounted Cost (2015-2017)

5. Discussion

In addition to implementing its NDC, Senegal is implementing a set of policies aimed at reducing its GHG emissions with a view to contributing to the global effort to reach the Paris Agreement limiting global warming to 1.5°C. At the same time, the country has begun to draw up long-term low-carbon development trajectories. However, it has to be said that all these measures were based on short-term planning that ignored the long-term co-benefits or limits. As such, the results of this work are intended to strengthen decision-making in the development of low-carbon or decarbonization strategies for the electricity sector over the long term. Although a number of efforts have been made to green electricity production, with a current penetration rate of over 30% for renewable energy, this work is intended to help strengthen sustainable energies in the long term. It will also help to inform decisions on the mitigation options available in this sub-sector over the long term, and the investment needed to implement them.

However, the country intends to exploit these hydrocarbon reserves (oil and gas) in the near future. In this context, the availability of lower-cost fossil resources could limit the implementation of these scenarios. What's more, the government intends to rely on these fossil resources, particularly natural gas, to increase electricity production and provide universal access to electricity in rural areas. Added to this is the high cost required to apply these scenarios, in that the technology costs are still a little high if storage is added. All these factors limit the application of these scenarios.

Although the government's energy policy guidelines remain essentially guided by universal access to energy services and energy sovereignty, taking account of the climate dimension remains just as vital as socio-economic development issues. In addition, the competitive projection of energies will limit the high demand for fossil fuels. Given these factors, renewable energies are an essential pillar both for increasing access to electricity and for helping to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

In view of the above, Senegal is currently at the crossroads of several energy and climate issues. This raises the question of the likely contribution of fossil fuels to financing the energy transition. In addition to the electricity sub-sector, the transition to clean cooking should be initiated by increasing the use of butane gas and electricity in order to reduce deforestation and other impacts associated with the use of wood and charcoal.

7. Conclusion

Although Senegal has significant potential for renewable energy (solar, wind, biomass) (New Climate Institute, 2023), most of its electricity is generated by fossil fuels. A generation that continuously takes into account the availability of gas resources, which the State intends to increase its electricity production.

In recent years, efforts have been made to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by producing electricity in a more low-carbon way. With an electricity mix of over 30%, the country plans to step up its efforts to 40% by 2030. In addition, the country's NDC specifies an increase of 699MW in renewable energy by 2030 to reduce emissions from the energy sector.

In addition to defining the mix rate forecast in the JETP with the necessary investment cost, this work explores ways of decarbonizing the electricity sub-sector in Senegal. This decarbonization would tend to cancel out investment in the sector from 2050 onwards. Although this scenario does not reflect exclusively renewable production, fossil fuels will be reduced over time.

The LoWC scenario requires more capacity to be installed than the BAU scenario, with a total investment cost of more than \$14 million. This calls for support from all stakeholders (government, private sector, banks and other technical and financial partners).

Furthermore, the availability of low-cost oil and gas resources should not limit the implementation of these scenarios. On the other hand, the financial resources generated by hydrocarbon production should help to support these scenarios.

However, given the high cost of storage and the intermittency of RE, it is recommended that gas-fired power stations be available in the long term. This is in order to make up for the disruption caused by intermittency, but also to maintain a trend towards reducing greenhouse gas emissions while waiting to develop sufficient storage capacity for renewable energies.

In the future, this work will be consolidated by a review and adjustment of certain data in order to better represent the Baseline scenario. Next, storage modelling will be initiated in order to obtain a better idea of the batteries required for the last two scenarios. Finally, other scenarios will be explored with a view to assessing the potential for using natural gas in the production sectors (transport and industry).

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